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The Iraqi Journal of Medicine has agreed the use of the uniform requirements of manuscripts submitted to biomedical journals published by the INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE OF MEDICAL JOURNAL EDITORS (ICMJE) and it's the first Iraqi peer journal listed by the ICMJE journal list. The first two issues of this journal appeared under the title of Al Karkh journal of Medicine

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Letter to the Editor

New International Association Formed to Address Global Medical Changes

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The International Association of Medical Colleges Medicine (IAOMC) has been formed to serve as the catalyst for assisting medical hospitals, Licensing Boards, and agencies around the world to effectively function in the ever accelerating inter communication and integration that is a part of the new global world. The mission of this non-stock, not for profit organization is to enhance world wide medical education by means of accreditation under uniform global standards. It is structured to interact in concert with the world's governing regulators. At the present, Association members are medical schools whose standards are ranked by the USDOE as substantially similar to medical schools in the United States. Membership in the IAOMC is open to the 1,684 medical schools currently

listed in the World Health Directory; and members of the 177 known regulatory agencies in the world. IAOMC invitations have been extended to all the world's qualified medical schools and regulatory agencies.

The IAOMC is a global response to the issue of varying medical education standards. It will be the world's first international medical school accreditor. In a challenge to traditional accreditation standards processes, every part of the Association process will be open and transparent. This is the first accreditation organization to end the mystery and secrecy that typically surrounds how most nations maintain medical education standards. Its public accountability will allow everyone to see exactly which schools are maintaining standards and

which ones are not. Everyone can obtain a copy of the Associations reports.

At a time of an ever-worsening physician shortage the Association's member schools responded. Approximately 3,000 of their clinical students are now studying across the United States. For example, IAOMC members have more clinical students

She will address the Association's standards meeting at the NY Hyatt on August 12th in her capacity as the Academic Director of Harvard Medical International. Pledged to be a fully open and democratic association, every medical school in the world within the World Health Directory (1,684) will be contacted for comment.

The Federation of State Medical Boards assisted by providing the list of every known regulatory agency in the world (177). They have each been invited to participate in the Association. Every Mission to the United Nations (190) has been notified to alert the medical schools and regulatory agencies in their nations. And the Regulatory Agencies were heard from. The interest is world wide, a few illustrations. After John P. Lamont, Registrar, of Ireland's Medical Council received notice of the standards meeting,

studying in New York State than the combined totals of Cornell University School of Medicine, Columbia University School of Medicine, NY State University of New York at Rochester, and State University of New York at Stony Brook. One of America's outstanding physicians, Dr. Lynn Eckert, is the Chair of the American Association of Medical Colleges.

and talked to Professor Muiris Fitzgerald, Chair of Education Committee. He has confirmed his attendance. Dorian Shillingford Chair of the Dominican Medical Board confirmed. Sheri Nichols, Alabama's Medical Board Secretary placed the invitation on the next Board meeting agenda. Bulgaria's UN Second Secretary Mrs. Anna Ruski will accompany Dr. Elena Piperkova from Sofia.

Invitations from the Association has drawn responses from such as Syed Ziaur Rahman, MD of Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College in India to **Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi MD, PhD. Of Al Kadhimiya Teaching Hospital in Iraq** to Michael Gordon from University of Toronto. All have submitted applications to serve as school on site inspectors.